

ASSESSMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC STRESS RESPONSES IN RATS WITH ANALYSIS OF ADRENALINE LEVELS AND BODY WEIGHT DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

The problem of stress responses in the body remains one of the key issues in modern physiology and pathophysiology, as stress underlies the development of a wide range of somatic and neuroendocrine disorders [1]. In recent years, particular attention has been paid to distinguishing the mechanisms of acute and chronic stress responses, since these conditions are characterized by fundamentally different adaptive and maladaptive effects [2].

Acute stress is considered an adaptive response aimed at mobilizing the body's resources, accompanied by activation of the sympathoadrenal system and an increase in catecholamine levels, particularly adrenaline [4]. At the same time, chronic stress leads to the exhaustion of regulatory systems, disruption of neuroendocrine balance, and the development of pathological changes, including metabolic and behavioral disorders [1].

Experimental models in rats are an important tool for studying the stress response, as they allow for precise control over the duration and intensity of exposure, as well as the assessment of physiological parameter dynamics [3]. Changes in adrenaline levels reflect the degree of activation of the sympathoadrenal system, whereas body weight dynamics serve as an integral indicator of metabolic status and the organism's adaptive capacity [5]. Despite a substantial body of research, issues related to the comparative assessment of acute and chronic stress responses using integrated indicators, including hormonal and morphofunctional parameters, remain insufficiently explored. In particular, elucidating the relationship between adrenaline levels and body weight changes under different types of stress exposure remains highly relevant. Thus, investigating the characteristics of acute and chronic stress responses in experimental animals is of significant importance for understanding the mechanisms of adaptation and for developing approaches to the

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Despite a substantial body of research, issues related to the comparative assessment of acute and chronic stress responses using integrated indicators, including hormonal and morphofunctional parameters, remain insufficiently explored. In particular, elucidating the relationship between adrenaline levels and body weight changes under different types of stress exposure remains highly relevant.

Thus, investigating the characteristics of acute and chronic stress responses in experimental animals is of significant importance for understanding the mechanisms of adaptation and for developing approaches to the correction of stress-induced disorders.

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Objective: To investigate the characteristics of neuroendocrine and metabolic changes under acute and chronic stress exposure in rats, with analysis of adrenaline levels and body weight dynamics.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in accordance with Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) standards. A total of 30 rats weighing 180–240 g were included and divided into control and experimental groups. Stress was induced using the forced swimming method in a cylindrical tank (height 40 cm, diameter 10 cm, water level 30 cm, temperature 20–23 °C) for 10 minutes daily.

Two stress models were evaluated: acute (4 days) and chronic (10 days). Blood samples were collected under ether anesthesia on days 4 and 10. Adrenaline levels were determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) at a wavelength of 450 nm. Body weight was measured daily using electronic scales. Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA with a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Under acute stress exposure (4 days), adrenaline levels increased from 830.75 ± 232.30 to 1127.50 ± 302.53 pg/mL ($p \leq 0.05$), indicating rapid activation of the sympathoadrenal system. Body weight in the animals decreased from 210.0 ± 11.73 to 203.0 ± 10.37 g, whereas a slight increase was observed in the control group.

Under chronic stress (10 days), adrenaline levels increased more markedly, reaching 1179.00 ± 351.92 pg/mL ($p \leq 0.05$), suggesting sustained activation of the neuroendocrine system. At the same time, a more pronounced decrease in body weight was observed—from 221.0 ± 20.12 to 204.0 ± 15.57 g—while in the control group body weight increased from 180.2 ± 24.55 to 190.0 ± 24.24 g.

Comparative analysis showed that the transition from acute to chronic stress is associated with an intensification of neuroendocrine and metabolic disturbances. Elevated adrenaline levels reflect the development of the resistance stage of the general adaptation syndrome, whereas body weight loss indicates the predominance of catabolic processes and disruption of energy balance.

Thus, the forced swimming model enables the reproduction of both early and prolonged mechanisms of the stress response, providing a comprehensive assessment of the organism's adaptive reactions.

Conclusions:

1. Acute and chronic stress induced by the forced swimming method is associated with a significant increase in plasma adrenaline levels. Chronic exposure leads to a more pronounced activation of the sympathoadrenal system (up to 1179.00 ± 351.92 pg/mL), reflecting the transition to the stage of sustained adaptation.

Stress exposure results in a decrease in body weight, which is more pronounced under chronic stress conditions. This indicates the progression of catabolic processes and disruption of energy homeostasis in the organism.

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